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Potential Risk Assessment of Rain Water Harvesting Sites in the Panjkora River Basin, Using Geospatial Techniques

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ABSTRACT

In the Panjkora River Basin, this study uses Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and Remote Sensing (RS) to examine the extent of vulnerability of rainwater harvesting (RWH) sites to natural catastrophes, particularly floods and debris flows. The study intends to evaluate the risks associated with both proposed (RWH_p) and existing (RWH_e) RWH sites because there aren't many comprehensive assessments of these hazards in this area. Despite the rising popularity of rainwater harvesting, gaps persist in assessing specific hazards like floods and debris flows. This study focuses on the Panjkora River Basin, utilizing advanced geospatial methods while considering current and future climate conditions. For improved risk understanding, the research divides hazard features into risk zones using sophisticated geospatial approaches, such as high-resolution digital elevation models. We identify compounded risk zones based on field validations and GIS overlay approaches using the RAMMS-DF model for debris flow simulations and HEC-RAS for flood scenarios. Significant debris flow threats are found at sites 15, 16, 17, and 19, and there is an elevated risk of flooding at site 10. There is variation in the risk landscape, with certain areas having low debris flow risk and others facing moderate flood hazards. In order to efficiently distribute water resources and create designed hazard management plans, stakeholders and legislators can benefit greatly from the important insights this research offers. Through the integration of modern GIS and modeling methodologies, we enhance awareness of environmental risks, disaster preparedness, and resource sustainability in the Panjkora River Basin, opening the way for informed decision-making in the region.

Keywords: Panjkora River Basin, GIS, Remote Sensing, Rainwater Harvesting, Flood Risk, Debris Flow, RAMMS-DF, HEC-RAS, Hazard Assessment, Climate Impact, Risk Zoning, Disaster Preparedness, Water Resource Management

1. INTRODUCTION

According to the World Economic Forum, the biggest long-term threat to civilization is the water crisis because of its devastating effects [1]. It is the most important component in Pakistan's agricultural resource output [2]. There are less than a thousand cubic meters of water available annually. nearly 191 million acre-feet of water will be accessible by 2025, as opposed to the nearly 274 million acre-feet that would be required [3]. Water scarcity has emerged as a key problem in Pakistan's discourse since achieving independence. The IMF highlights the critical importance of water for survival by stating that, in the absence of strong conservation efforts, the nation may become completely dry by 2025. Serious water difficulties are transforming Pakistan's security, so stability and advancement depend on finding a solution [4]. Pakistan is currently facing a water crisis brought on by drought-like circumstances brought on by problems with dams and canals, low

water quality, issues with sewerage, and climate variables [5]. Water is necessary for all life and biodiversity because it fulfills a number of functions in the ecosystem. Due to low storage capacity, poor infiltration, irregular precipitation, and high evaporation rates, water scarcity affects both arid regions and locations with enough rainfall [6]. Water-related resources increase agricultural productivity by offering crucial irrigation techniques and putting effective water collection and conservation measures in place [7]. Rainwater harvesting (RWH) is crucial because a significant amount of runoff water leaves the catchment as surface runoff [8]. Rainwater collection is gaining popularity as a less expensive alternative to irrigation [9]. The technique of collecting and storing rainwater for future use is known as rainwater harvesting. It also entails replenishing groundwater wells and controlling flooding [10]. Rainwater harvesting sites are vital to improving water supplies in Pakistan's arid regions, but they face many challenges due to natural disasters. Although flash floods in hill areas could completely wash away these systems, intermittent heavy monsoon showers may cause water overflow or damage. In addition, the infrastructure and adaptation landscape are also exposed to cyclones and landslides making it difficult to manage water shortage effectively.

In the steep topography of the north, debris flows that bury collecting systems behind sediment are especially problematic. These inherent vulnerabilities are compounded by the effects of climate change, which is causing more extreme weather-related events. The government has invested in alternative rainwater catchment areas, but there are concerns about economic loss and inefficiency since these areas are prone to natural hazards. Hence, to enhance the resilience of rainwater catchment systems to floods and debris flows, a multistakeholder strategy incorporating engineering measures, community engagement, and disaster risk reduction is imperative. Risk assessment and management to rainwater harvesting systems are facilitated with the application of Geographic Information System (GIS) technology, especially with the increasing number of hydro-meteorological disasters across the globe that bring about property and human losses.[11]. Flooding is a global catastrophe that impacts billions of people residing in flood-stricken areas[12]. Floods are among the most destructive natural disasters due to the union of climatic and hydrological factors[13]. Greater intensity of heavy rain reflects a greater probability of catastrophic floods, and the importance of modern river engineering and floodplain management methods in refining flood risk assessment[14]. In steep terrain, debris flows are particularly perilous natural hazards, as well as other landslide types. One of the primary triggering causes of a debris flow from the initial landslide is rain[15]. Because usually little is known about the initiating conditions, such as periods of heavy rainfall, it is hard to generate a good debris flow prediction.[16]. A crucial

process for establishing the likelihood and potential impacts of debris flows on property, individuals, and economic activity is a debris flow hazard assessment[17]. This is particularly so in hilly regions where debris flows pose grave natural threats.[18]. The potential for landslides is increasingly evident due to increased understanding of the influence of urbanization on landslide hazards.[19]. Metering land parameters such as volume of trash, speed of flow, and distance results in the watershed hazard scale. Due to leaks of hazardous material during natural disasters, which enhances the risks of catastrophic accidents, debris flow modeling is required for developing safety protocols and risk maps.[11]. Pakistan's Eastern Hindukush is highly threatened by floods and debris flows, especially in the Panjkora River Basin, which is struggling to cope with its water resources.

Applying GIS and remote sensing methods, this research will analyze how susceptible rainwater harvesting systems are to different natural hazards. Ultimately, it will assist the region in making more efficient use of water resources and minimizing the risk of disasters by analyzing their performance under severe weather conditions, indicating risk determinants, and proposing safety and resilience strategies. Due to its varied topography and climate, Pakistan is vulnerable to a wide range of natural disasters in its northern, coastal, and southern areas, including avalanches, landslides, earthquakes, cyclones, flooding, and droughts [20]. Pakistan has seen a sharp rise in devastating floods despite efforts to manage rivers, resulting in severe loss of life and property. In recent years, millions have been affected and hundreds have died [20]. Since Pakistan gained independence in 1947, 90% of the country's population has been affected by natural catastrophes; in August 2010, the country saw its biggest flood in recorded history, which resulted in around 1,800 fatalities and tens of billions of dollars in damages [21]. From 1947 to 2015, there were twenty-three significant floods in Pakistan, with the worst being in 2010 and hitting areas including Gilgit-Baltistan, Punjab, KPK, AJK, and Sindh[22]. Pakistan is severely affected by climate change and frequently experiences natural catastrophes like floods and droughts. Inadequate mitigation measures have a negative impact on millions of people and have caused five consecutive floods between 2010 and 2015 [23]. In many parts of Southeast and South Asian countries, floods have become increasingly regular and intense in recent decades. As a result, China, Bangladesh, India, and Pakistan have been recognized as hotspots of catastrophe.[23]. Pakistan frequently experiences massive flooding, either riverine or flash. This can cause widespread damage to land, crops, and infrastructure, particularly during the monsoon period, which extends from July through September.[24]. In the last 25 to 30 years, the effects of climate change have contributed to an escalation in the frequency and intensity of floods, a principal reason for casualties and financial loss throughout South Asia.[25].

The Geographic Information System (GIS) combines digital image processing and remote sensing to provide risk reduction alternatives, like new dams, to accurately assess flood risk in sensitive areas, particularly along Pakistan's Indus River.[25]. With their snow peaks, steep slopes, glaciers, and intense seismicity, Northern Pakistan is vulnerable to frequent natural disasters like flash floods and landslides.[26]. Eight various types of mass motions have been reported in the Karakoram Mountains: rotating slips, slumps, rock falls, avalanches, rockslides, debris flow, and creep.[27]. Debris flows and flow slides are common mass movements in the Karakoram triggered by severe weather patterns, high winds, earthquakes, and poor land use.[28].

Due to the challenging terrain of Gilgit Baltistan, where 90% of the region consists of mountains, debris flows, flash floods, and Glacier Lake Outburst Floods (GLOFs) are a common occurrence.[29]. With an upsurge of extreme weather conditions such as the heatwave of 2022 and the devastating flooding that ensued—comprising debris flows and glacial lake outburst floods, especially in Gilgit-Baltistan during heavy monsoon rains or snowmelt and Pakistan is highly susceptible to climate change[26]. A major geological hazard, debris flows affect not just the local community but also the Karakoram Highway (KKH), a critical corridor for transportation between China and Pakistan by.[30]. Significant geological threats are posed by debris flows, which not only affect the local community but also the Karakoram Highway (KKH), a critical corridor for transport which connects China and Pakistan. [31]. There have been reportedly 150 debris flows over the Karakoram Highway (KKH) between 2008-2011. Flooding is a significant threat to rainwater harvesting systems because it has the potential to cause overflow, erosion, and obstruction by debris, which can result in damage or destruction. Thus, disaster planning and robust design are critical. Debris flows, which can cover infrastructure in rainwater harvesting systems with mud and debris, can break pipelines and damage components, are a significant danger to the systems. For such systems to be resilient and continue to operate during such natural disasters, efficient risk assessment, mitigation, and proactive maintenance are crucial. The research assesses risks, geographically locates and assesses damage through GIS and RS techniques, and studies the influence of floods and debris flows on rainwater collecting locations in the Panjkora River Basin. In addition, it examines strategies to strengthen these areas so that the region can become more disaster-resistant and sustainably manage water. The overall purpose of this research is to evaluate the possible hazard threat of floods and debris flow to the current and newly proposed/planned water conservation areas within the research area. This aim will be achieved through the following specific objectives (a) To figure out the flood hazard at multiple Panjkora river basin locations. (b) To assess the potential for debris flow hazards at both planned and

existing water harvesting locations. (c) To assign a risk rating of low, moderate, and high for flood and debris flow hazards to both existing and proposed sites. This study will assess the vulnerability of rainwater harvesting sites in the Panjkora River basin to debris flows and floods, helping identify at-risk areas and the extent of potential damage. The findings will aid authorities in understanding and mitigating risks to these sites.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Study Area

The Panjkora River and its principal tributaries drain a significant geographic area known as the Panjkora River Basin, which is located in the Eastern Hindu Kush of Northwest Pakistan. The area sees catastrophic flooding, such as the flood of 2022 that destroyed rainwater harvesting infrastructure, due to the region's dry winters and intense monsoon rains, which fall from June to September. Because of the area's high slopes, there is a greater chance of debris flows, avalanches, and landslides, all of which can worsen damage to these systems.

2.2 Data Sources

Although high-resolution DEMs may strain system resources and result in crashes due to insufficient processing power, the study uses a 12.5-meter resolution DEM from ALOS PALSAR for HEC-RAS flood simulations, created by JAROS and the Japanese Space Agency. The Peshawar irrigation department provides the Panjkora River's discharge data, which is crucial for HEC-RAS flood analysis since it allows for exact simulations of flow behavior, flood extents, and risk assessment. In order to guarantee that rainwater harvesting systems are installed securely and continue to function even in the event of floods or debris flows, high-resolution satellite imagery is crucial for locating and tracking susceptible locations. In order to identify flood dangers and perform more accurate flood predictions and better preparations like levees and early warnings, Manning's Value is essential to determine the velocity of water flow. In October 2023, a field trip in the Panjkora River basin was carried out to collect vast data on topography and local conditions. This includes the checking of rainwater harvesting sites that where it is

located and shows how hazard overflow there such as flood and debris flow also use the GPS System to make sure these sites are safe and sound and also work well during hazard such as flood and debris flow.

2.3 Identification of Key Influencing Factors

In HEC-RAS, normally we do see the water pattern, especially in flood and hazard form. In the initial stage, we will try to understand the land shape where the hazard causes like we will first understand a little triangle we normally called it TIN. It is because those shapes will help the hec ras to understand and observe hills, valleys, and bumps better. In this way, the hecras will understand the water movement, how fast it will go, how deep it will be, and where it goes. The middle line in the river is the centerline and is considered a really important factor in this analysis. It shows the main sketch of the river, how it will react, how spread it is, and how steep it is. And this help us to create cross sections to understand how rough and smooth the river is. In this analysis, the river edge, also called banks, also needs to be drawn. This will help the software determine how wide the river is and how it will react during heavy rainfall. The way is made to present where the flow of water will pass, and then the HEC-RAS will understand how flood water will move in that area. After that, the map is created to present which area will face flood, and eventually the people in that area can be kept safe, and also the rainwater harvesting sites will be kept in notice.

The river cross-section is another necessary element for HEC-RAS flood analysis because it will show the shape and size of the river body. Accurate cross sections can increase the prediction rate of how far and where the flood will go. This also helps to understand the model and study flood risks better. and it will help in reducing the flood damage to people and rainwater harvesting sites as well. The water flow is defined through a value called Manning's n. It's a number between 0.008 to 0.50 for flood plains, which defines how fast the water moves. A small value means slow flow, and a high value means faster flow and less resistance from the ground. It is crucial for determining the likelihood of flooding and erosion in floodplains and is impacted by the geometry and roughness of the channel. Based on topographic data, the RAMMS debris flow model's simulation accuracy is affected by the resolution of the DEM. The direction of flow is determined by elevation differences, and before being loaded into the application, topographic raster files are translated using ArcGIS to ESRI ASCII format for RAMMS compatibility. To make sense of the DEM which appears as a white tint that makes it difficult to detect release areas an orthomosaic picture of the research zone is put into RAMMS. For improved visualization, the image which must be in TIFF format automatically overlays the DEM. For RAMMS debris flow modeling, it is essential to specify friction characteristics. Dry-Coulomb (μ) and viscous-turbulent () components of friction are separated

using the Voellmy-fluid model. Several iterations tuned μ between 100 and 1000 m/s² and μ between 0.05 and 0.4. Since there was no available data on debris flow intensity for comparison, changes were performed by isolating parameters, taking into account the shape of the depositional zone and runout distance, due to the lack of local literature for the Panjkora river basin.

The operation of the model depends on determining the release site, making this research stage critical and difficult. To collect historical data, we used high-resolution Google Earth Pro photos and community gatherings. Because of the loose sediments, it was suggested that the discovered region might be a likely release point.

For the model, determining the release volume is essential after determining the release region. Based on the measured depositional heights, this volume varies between the scenarios, all of which are higher than the previous ones. Every scenario has one release area, while some have two if multiple volumes are issued at the same time.

After defining the watershed input zone and adjusting parameters like release area, volume, density, and friction, the simulations start. The model operates in block releases, with the length of each block varying based on processing power and complexity. RAMMS tools are used to assess the results, and until the intended results are obtained, adjustments to the parameters are made repeatedly.

2.4 Implementation of Methodology

2.4.1 HEC-RAS Use for Flood

Equation 3.2 is used to calculate water surface profiles in HEC-RAS, a river flood simulation program created by the US Army Corps of Engineers.

$$Z_2 + Y_2 + \frac{a_2 V_2^2}{2g} = Z_1 + Y_1 + \frac{a_1 V_1^2}{2g} + h_e$$

(3.2)

The elevation of the main channel inverts is shown by Z1 and Z2, the water depths at cross sections are indicated by Y1 and Y2, the average velocities (total discharge/total flow area) are represented by V1 and V2, the gravitational acceleration is indicated by g, and the energy head loss is indicated by h_e . A modeling method called HEC-RAS examines channel elevation, water depth, and flow velocity to mimic river water flow during floods. It uses fluid mechanics energy equations to estimate the heights of water surfaces while taking friction losses and elevation changes into account. As a result, HEC-RAS is essential for efficient flood risk assessment and management. It also helps with flood hazard assessments and infrastructure design for risk reduction by providing precise water level estimations.

2.4.2 RAMMS-DF Use for Debris Flow

A comprehensive program called RAMMS (Rapid Mass Movements)

combines safety and visualization components with modules for snow avalanches, debris flows, and rock falls. It simulates debris flow using a one-phase Voellmy-Fluid model under the assumption of no shear deformation. The friction slope in this model is given by Eq. 3.1, and the flow body acts like a plug with a constant mean velocity (u).

$$S = \mu \rho g h \cos(\theta) + (\rho g u^2) / \dots \quad (3.1)$$

The terrain's downslope angle (ϕ) is taken into account when modeling in RAMMS. The flow law divides debris flow resistance into two categories: velocity-dependent viscous resistance (ξ) and dry Coulomb friction (μ) using a calibrated, depth-averaged continuum model. The finite volume method is used to solve shallow water equations in three-dimensional terrain. The resistance values μ and ξ , as well as the overall volume of debris flow from approved release sites, are input parameters[32].

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Rainwater Harvesting (RWH) Sites

Rainwater harvesting sites are essential for managing water resources in areas with erratic supply, like the topographically diversified Panjkora river basin. This region makes use of a variety of rainwater harvesting (RWH) sites, such as ground catchment areas, check dams, and rooftop catchment systems. Since rooftop systems collect and store rainwater directly from buildings, they are useful in crowded locations with little space. Agriculture benefits from check dams, which are little barriers that span streams and improve groundwater recharge. They also lessen soil erosion. Normally, water in mountainous region flows from up to down due to elevations and gravity, and then is stored in one place we call it catchment areas. And these are usually in high places. The rainwater harvesting sites are really important for managing the water supply in this region. These sites are at high risk in those areas because of heavy rainfall, which eventually causes hazards like floods and debris flow. Due to which the stones and mud, and other material flow with itself, and these sites come in the way, due to which it can break down. Software like HEC-RAS and RAMMS-DF have shown that these risks are real. When these hazards cause blockage or sometimes break the sites, especially in steep places. Due to this, it is important to study these risks and manage them. In this manner, the rainwater harvesting sites will work well and last a long time.

3.2 Flood Hazard

The output shows clear how a hazard like flood risk rwh sites in the

panjkora river basin. This helps us understand how floods will affect rainwater harvesting sites. The flood categories are shown in three forms: high, medium, and low. The darkest in color on the map shows the highest flood danger; the rwh sites in these areas will be damaged badly. lighter areas still have a serious risk, especially if the land is steep a lot of loose soil. Medium color areas have a moderate flood risk, which can still be dangerous for rwh sites. This map also shows where current RWH sites are located in relation to these flood zones and how likely they are to be harmed by floods.

3.2.1 Proposed RWH sites vs Flood Hazard

These sites in the panjkora river basin have different level of flood risk. Site 10 in this scene is in a high-risk zone, so if a big flood happens, it could be badly damaged and stop working. There are flood hazards at Site 11 as well, but they are not as significant as at Site 10 and would lead to moderate damage to infrastructure. so these sites show how useful it is to examine and study flood risks so that we can reduce the threat to rainwater harvesting sites in this area.

It is anticipated that Site 12, which is located in a moderate flood zone and is in the highest risk category, will see deep flooding. This hazard causes a big issue for how the sites work and might lead to serious damage. Site 13 is located in the moderate flood risk area and zone, where the flood level varies; this shows how it is important to study this hazard in the Panjkora River basin. Site 14, which is situated in a moderate flood zone as well, illustrates how common this danger is in the basin and the necessity of ongoing surveillance and flood control measures to safeguard these crucial infrastructure systems.

3.2.2 Existing RWH Sites vs Flood Hazard

The analysis created two files for flood depth and velocity. It focused on rainwater collection sites in the Panjkora river basin. The first site is moderately flood-prone, while Site 2 was completely destroyed as it is in a high-risk zone. Site 3 is in a moderate flood zone, so it will be damaged. Site 5, Site 6, and Site 8 were all destroyed due to their locations in the moderately flooded zone of the Panjkora river basin. This is detailed in figure 4.2 of the Rainwater Harvesting Locations. The research found that Site 1 and Site 3 are both in moderate flood areas, making them prone to damage during floods, as shown in figure 4.2. The HEC-RAS model provided flood velocity information for the Panjkora river basin. Some rainwater sites, like Site 2, are in areas with low flood velocities, while Site 6 is in moderate flood speed zones. Even with lower velocities, sites could still be submerged and destroyed. Sites 1, 3, 5, 6, and 8 are at higher risk due to the combined effects of flood depth and velocity. This is detailed in figure 4.2.

3.3 Debris Flow

3.3.1 Proposed RWH Sites Vs Debris Flow

The risk of debris flow varies among the suggested rainwater

harvesting (RWH) sites. Site 10 is less vulnerable to harm because of its low danger of debris flow. Sites 11, 12, and 13 are classified as low risk, meaning that while harm could occur there, it wouldn't be as bad as in high-risk regions. Site 14 appears to be reasonably safe as there is no concern of debris flow. However, there is a high probability of debris flow at Sites 15, 16, and 17, making them extremely dangerous. Last but not least, Site 18 is less likely to sustain significant damage because to its low debris flow danger. Like Site 10, Site 19 is not at high danger of debris flow.

3.3.2 Existing RWH Sites Vs Debris Flow

Debris flow poses a serious concern to existing rainwater harvesting (RWH) systems at locations 4 and 7. This suggests that the infrastructure and rainwater collection operations could be severely disrupted and the areas are extremely susceptible to debris flow disasters. These locations are extremely dangerous because of the high risk rating, which indicates that any debris flow in the area could have negative consequences.

3.4 Risk Assessment

3.4.1 Risk Assessment of Proposed RWH Sites

All of the suggested sites for rainwater collection that fall within the various risk assessment zones for debris flow and flooding are shown in Table 4.1.

4.1 Risk Assessment of Proposed RWH sites

Proposed Sites#	Risk Assessment	Type of Hazard
10	High	Flood
	Low	Debris Flow
11	Moderate	Flood
	Low	Debris Flow
12	Moderate	Flood
	Low	Debris Flow
13	Moderate	Flood
	Low	Debris Flow
14	Moderate	Flood
	No Risk	Debris Flow
15 & 16	Extreme	Debris Flow
17	Extreme	Debris Flow
18	Low	Debris Flow
19	High	Debris Flow

Potential flood and debris flow hazards are highlighted in the risk assessment for the suggested locations in the Panjkora River basin. Site 10 has a low danger of debris flow but a high risk of flooding. Sites 11 and 12 exhibit low concerns for debris flow and moderate flood threats, with some but not significant water buildup. Similar to Site 13, Site 13 has a small danger of flooding and little trouble with debris flow. With no probability of debris flow, Site 14 is categorized as having a moderate flood risk. Sites 15 and 16, on the other hand, are less concerned about flooding but have a high risk of debris flow. Additionally, there is a significant risk of debris flow at Site 17 without significant flood hazards. Site 18 exhibits minimal concerns for debris flow and floods. Finally, Site 19 is not at risk for flooding, but it is at high risk for debris flow. Understanding the unique dangers at each area is made easier by this assessment.

Figure 4.14 Pie Chart Representation of flood RWH Sites

Figure 4.15 Representation of debris flow RWH Sites

3.4.2 Risk Assessment of Existing RWH Sites

All of the existing sites for rainwater harvesting that are entering the various risk assessment zones for debris flow and flooding are shown in Table 4.2.

4.2 Risk Assessment of Existing RWH Sites

Existing sites#	Risk Assessment	Type of Hazard
1	Moderate	Flood
2	Low	Flood
3	Moderate	Flood
4	Extreme	Debris Flow
5	Moderate	Flood
6	Moderate	Flood
7	Extreme	Debris Flow
8	Moderate	Flood

Figure 4.2 shows how the risk assessment for the existing site

assesses the possible risks of debris flow and flooding. The risk assessment for the existing sites highlights the dangers of debris flow and flooding. Site 1 displays signs of a moderate flood in the area, indicating that water buildup may occur here during periods of intense precipitation or from other causes. Site 2 displays the zone's flood risk while accounting for the least amount of water accumulation in the area. This is comparable to Site 1 and suggests a moderate danger of flooding, according to Site 3. Site 4 demonstrates that it is located in debris flow high-risk areas. Site 5 indicates that there is a moderate risk of flooding in this area. Site 6 indicates that there is a moderate chance of flooding. Site 8 displays a moderate level of flooding in the Panjkora River basin, whereas Site 7 shows a high level of debris flow risk in the region. The region's debris flow RWH Sites risk assessment is graphically represented in Figure 4.16.

Figure 4.16 P Representation of Flood and Debris Flow RWH Site4. CONCLUSIONS

In study area Panjkora river basin, HEC-RAS and RAMMS-DF models were used to study how much risk there is from hazards like flood and debris flows to rainwater harvesting sites. This analysis shows that the risk is not the same at every site; some areas have a bigger chance of flood hazard or even being hit by debris flow in the zones.

This implies that vulnerability is heavily impacted by environmental and geographic factors. The results highlight how poor the existing site placements are and call for a re-evaluation and adjustment of strategies. The research underlines the importance of evidence-driven decision-making for managing environmental risks and urges adoption of site-specific risk assessments and utilization of high-end modeling tools to enhance the efficacy and safety of rainwater harvesting systems.

Numerous recommendations are made on the basis of advanced modeling techniques to enhance the vulnerability of rainwater collection areas in the Panjkora river basin against

flooding and debris flows. Initially, to prepare for and understand such disasters, an integrated risk assessment plan that includes historical information, current conditions, and projected climate change should be adopted. This strategy will incorporate information on debris flow and floods. It's also essential to improve construction methods in dangerous areas, like the construction of levees, platform heightening, and the utilization of flood-resistant materials. Proactive alerts can also be sent to site managers by implementing early warning systems and real-time monitoring. Routine maintenance and inspection of debris management structures and flood control structures to tackle issues such as erosion and structural performance are essential.

To low down the level of damage caused by hazards such as floods and debris flow, it's really important to have warning and indication systems. This setup will inform the operators and the management about the incoming danger in no time. It is also necessary to have strong buildings, better drainage systems, and other policies that encourage people. Plan for risk, design, and quick emergency response should be used. By utilizing these techniques, flood and debris flow will be reduced, and the rainwater harvesting sites in the assigned area will be more secure.

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